

File “InSAR_F1_F2_F3_vlm.txt” contains the InSAR results from manuscript “Fanghui Deng. Current subsidence rates of the Mississippi River Delta from Satellite radar interferometry: onshore and offshore. Under review (as of April 2025).”

The file includes the uncalibrated and calibrated InSAR rates at all PS points (for offshore region, both active and non-active platforms are included). The file contains 5 columns:

“lon” is longitude of PS point on the WGS84 WGS84 ellipsoid;

“lat” is latitude of PS point on the WGS84 WGS84 ellipsoid;

“rate_LOS_uncalibrated_mm/year” is uncalibrated InSAR rate in the line-of-sight direction;

“rate_LOS_calibrated_mm/year” is calibrated InSAR rate in the line-of-sight direction;

“rate_calibrated_vertical_mm/year” is the calibrated InSAR rate converted to the vertical direction.

The rates all have a unit of mm/year.